

EMB3Rs

Heat and Cold matching platform

D5.1 – WP5 Final Report

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Technical References

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¹ PU = Public

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Summary

Work Package 5 – Platform Scalability and Deployment used a combination of the insights from WP4 Sector-Specific Platform Demonstration, desktop research, lessons learned from previous work in the RHC (residual heat and cold) domain and interviews with experts and practitioners to address the following tasks:

- **T 5.1 Scalability and Replicability of Proposed Solutions**
- **T 5.2 Industry Wide Solutions and Multi-Sectorial Applications**
- **T 5.3 Path to Finance and Wide-Scale Deployment of Waste Heat/Cold Recovery**

Task 5.1 first analyses the replicability of the solutions by comparing the context and scope of the problems solved in the seven Case Studies to those of the overall, real-life industrial environment that the EMB3Rs platform can be expected to tackle. Next, the potential to scale the platform is assessed based on two main factors – limits to its functionality and data requirements.

The assessment of the replicability of solutions was carried out in a systematic way for each parameter defining the scope of solutions, sources, sinks and grid that was identified as relevant for the replicability. An overview of the findings is provided in Table 1 below. It shows that to a large extent, the platform has covered in the Case Studies the relevant range of the problems that it can be expected to encounter when applied to real-life problems outside of the project, and be expected to replicate valid solutions. The one exception to this is the number of sinks, where the range covered by the platform were two orders of magnitude lower than the biggest district heating networks in existence currently. However, the platform is not intended to model problems of this scale, as this is the domain of dedicated teams of RHC experts with professional, commercial tools. For all other central parameters of the RHC use, the solutions provided by the platform demonstrate that it can cover the entire range of potential problems which it will be applied to.

Category	Parameter	Covered in the seven EMB3Rs Case Studies	Assessment
RHC solutions and use cases	Scope of solutions on the RHC use cascade	All three levels associated with RHC use (internal, external, conversion)	EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
	RHC use cases	All use cases except feeding RHC into low- and extra-low DHN	Identical physical and modelling principles apply: EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
Sources	Number of sources	Same order of magnitude as (very) large DHNs	EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
	Supply temperatures	High (till ~650°C) but not very high (above 1,000°C)	Identical physical and modelling principles apply: EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade. However, it is up to user to consider potential adverse affects (e.g. corrosion) on equipment associated with very high temperatures
	Heat carrying mediums	Flue gases, air and water; no steam, thermal oil, milk and whey concentrate	Identical physical and modelling principles apply: EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
	Heat energy transfer levels	Entire range	EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
	Shut down-periods	A high degree of complexity covered	EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
Sinks	Number of sinks	Up to two orders of magnitude below largest real-life DHNs	The platform cannot necessarily be expected to solve problems larger by two orders of magnitude due to computational limitations (which can be overcome if the user provides those themselves); but modelling entire very large DHNs falls out of the expected scope of platform use so this limitation is not as significant
	Heat carrying mediums	Water and steam; no air	Identical physical and modelling principles apply: EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
	Target temperatures	Most relevant ranges covered except low and extra low and high temperature extremes	Identical physical and modelling principles apply: EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade.
	Heat energy transfer levels	Very large sources not covered	Identical physical and modelling principles apply: EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
Grid	Total length	Most of the relevant range covered, except for extreme upward outliers	EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire range
	Heat transfer capacity	Not possible to compare to real-life environment	Identical physical and modelling principles apply across the entire range: EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties covering the entire cascade
	Use of heat storage	Covered	EMBR3s platform should encounter no difficulties simulating storage in real-life environment

Table 1: Overview of the solutions replicability assessment

The assessment of scalability looks at two main factors: EMB3Rs platform functionalities and its data needs. For platform functionalities, it identifies three limitations to its function which may limit its usefulness for solving some real-life problems. These are:

- **Inability to model grids with meshed topologies**, defined as grids where heat can travel from A to B in more than one way. The reason for this is the substantial modelling complexity which would have been required for that. In practice, larger DHNs tend to be meshed, whereas smaller ones tend not to be meshed. As the EMB3Rs platform is intended to be used for initial prospecting of RHC viability rather than for modelling highly complex grids, and because a workaround can be used, the practical limitations for its usability can be expected to not be significant.
- **Inability to model a backup heat source behind the meter (or “inside a sink”)**, which might be required to raise the temperature level of the supplied heat or meet the sink’s requirements in times of low source availability. This too is likely to have a limited impact on platform’s availability since it is only relevant for internal nodes in a grid, which tend to be more prevalent with grids of higher sizes and complexities.
- **Inability to distinguish between baseline and peak sources of heat**, which would be required to optimise the costs of heat supply, e.g. if the potential peak heat source is much further away and costs for running the circulation pumps are much higher than for the would-be baseline source. Being able to draw this distinction would improve solutions provided by the EMB3Rs platform on the margins, but does not diminish its key ability to provide a first assessment of RHC solutions’ viability.

The second factor that will play a role in scaling the use of the platform are data requirements. As was anticipated before the project and confirmed during it, availability of RHC-specific data can represent a challenge. The project partners implementing the seven Case Studies who had had time to prepare and approach data collection in a systematic way had no issues overcoming this challenge. The same systematic approach to data collection will generally have to be applied by the future users of the EMB3Rs platform. To reduce the workload associated with this step, the EMB3Rs platform makes the following provisions:

- **Limiting the overall data required to a minimum**
- **Providing the user with a degree of flexibility in terms level of the level of detail of the input data**
- **Providing the user with guidance on what exact data is necessary**
- **Providing a wide range of default values and other types of inputs from its Knowledge Base, to be used when more accurate data is not available**
- **Making the necessary provisions for data management on the platform itself**

In this way, the platform strikes the optimal balance between lowering the threshold for its use in the domain of required input data, while staying committed to being capable of providing relevant and reliable solutions.

Task 5.2 deals with Industry Wide Solutions and Multi-Sectorial Applications by implementing the following steps and deriving the following insights:

- **Development of NFR-based ontology for industrial energy management systems:** This task constructed an ontology model that captures the non-functional requirements (NFRs) and their critical factors for the energy domain and industrial energy management systems (IEMS). The ontology model defines classes, properties, and relations to represent the NFRs and their factors, such as regulations, stakeholders, technologies, and markets. The ontology model was evaluated using various methods, such as technical validation, user evaluations, RDF data

management, and application-based evaluation. The results indicated that the ontology model enhanced data integration, interoperability, and scalability of the platform, and supported software development in the EMB3Rs project. The ontology model also helped to quantify potential reductions in energy consumption, emissions, waste generation, and other environmental impacts associated with implementing cleaner and more sustainable solutions.

- **MCDM-based Analysis for Excess Heat Utilization:** This task conducted a comprehensive analysis of the excess heat utilization options using a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) approach. MCDM is a decision-making methodology that assists decision-makers in selecting the best alternative among multiple conflicting criteria, such as economic, environmental, and social factors. The MCDM model was applied to the EMB3Rs project by collecting data on nine excess heat utilization options and 13 criteria and sub-criteria from various sources. The data were normalized and used to create a hierarchy of criteria and sub-criteria. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used to assign weights to them based on their importance or relevance in the decision-making process. The weighted score and rank for each alternative were computed based on their performance against the criteria and sub-criteria. To facilitate the use of the proposed MCDM, an online tool has been created for user interaction, and to identify the top-ranked options for excess heat utilization.
- **Decision model for assessing EMB3Rs platform applicability to other use cases:** This task investigated the applicability of the EMB3Rs platform to other use cases beyond those considered in the project using a decision tree-based model. A use case is a specific scenario or application that involves excess heat recovery and utilization in an industrial setting. The decision tree model identified the primary properties that may vary from one use case to another, such as excess heat source type, temperature level, availability, demand type and location, utilization option, market potential, and environmental impact. These properties affect the excess heat recovery and utilization process and the suitability of the platform for different use cases. The decision tree model was applied to various use cases from other EU projects and evaluated their suitability based on a score that ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 means not suitable and 1 means fully suitable. The results revealed that the EMB3Rs platform is suitable for most of the use cases considered, except for those with very low excess heat availability (<10%) or very high distance between source and demand (>50 km). The results also identified potential challenges and opportunities for improvement for each use case.

Task 5.3. analyses the challenges, solutions and financing options for RHC use and provides policy recommendations for wide-scale RHC deployment. It identifies the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for five EU member states' most relevant RHC support programmes (Austria, Denmark, Germany, Greece and Portugal). The main finding is that in the three north and central European countries, there are programmes addressing RHC use specifically, with dedicated support schemes and funds, whereas in Greece and Portugal no comparable schemes exist and RHC use projects are required to qualify based on the same criteria as other

energy and THG saving measures with considerably lower investment capital requirements and complexities, putting them at disadvantage.

The recommendations for facilitating a wide-scale use of RHC focus on three main action areas for the member states:

- **Establishing a comprehensive and reliable data basis specifically for RHC use, by**
 - Systematic bottom-up RHC data collection, e.g. within the framework of obligatory energy audits and certified energy management systems.
 - **Systematic sharing of RHC-relevant data** at least on local level
 - **RHC potential analysis on local, not just national level, e.g. by** involving energy agencies

- **Providing support schemes addressing capital expenditure of external RHC use projects, by**
 - Providing dedicated support schemes for RHC projects
Avoid making RHC projects compete for funding against simpler measures with far lower complexities, capital requirements and payback periods.
 - Making sure that all steps of the value chain of RHC project are addressed by the support programmes
 - Providing grants at or at least close to the maximum levels allowed under the EU law
 - Aligning the incentives with desired effects
 - Making the support schemes as user-friendly as possible
 - Reducing deadweight on the support programmes

- **Assisting with de-risking in the following four main domains of RHC use**
 - Risk of outages of heat sources or connections, e.g. by explicitly adding risk assessment or adding further criteria for selecting the projects
 - Counterparty risk, e.g. by developing corresponding insurance products in including them into RHC use support schemes
 - Risk of excessive opportunity costs, same as above
 - Capital market risks by providing loans with long durations of set interest rates to RHC and DHN projects

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